

MODELLING AND EXPERIMENTAL CHARACTERISATION OF PHASE STRAIN EVOLUTION IN 10 VOL% AL/SiC_w COMPOSITE DURING THERMO MECHANICAL LOADING

T. Lorentzen and Y. L. Liu

Materials Department, Risø National Laboratory, P.O. Box 49, Roskilde, Denmark

SUMMARY: This paper addresses the experimental characterisation of the phase strain response to thermo mechanical loading using neutron diffraction, with the aim to evaluate numerical predictions of phase strain evolution. By the use of neutron diffraction we characterise the initial residual phase strains in the two phases of a 10vol% Al/SiC_w composite. When compared to numerical simulations by the Finite Element Method (FEM), it is apparent, that such predictions over estimates the thermal residual phase strains. FEM-simulations of subsequent room temperature loading shows some discrepancies as compared to neutron diffraction experiments, though the phase strain evolution is qualitatively in agreement with the experimental evidence. It is evident that the cell-model idealisation of real composites does not accurately reflect the real state of internal stress development in the two constituent phases.

KEYWORDS: neutron diffraction, residual stresses, thermal stresses, internal stresses, finite element method, phase strains, Al/SiC, in-situ

INTRODUCTION

Metal matrix composites are born with an inherent mis-match in both coefficients of thermal expansions and elastic/plastic deformation characteristics. It is well known that this leads to a state of initial residual strains and stresses in the composites during the production phase. Subsequent loading will first of all be affected by these residual strains, but further more this will also develop internal mis-match strains and stresses due to the incompatibility in deformation characteristics.

The generation of phase strains and stresses are typically modelled by the FEM cell-model approach [1-3] which, however, is an idealisation of the real composite consisting of many inclusions. Despite that such FEM-simulations may render realistic results judged on the macroscopic deformation of the composite, the individual phase strain evolution, and the microstructural reasoning for the qualitatively correct macroscopic properties is still uncertain. In order to evaluate the quality of these popular FEM cell-models on a microstructural level this calls for experimental techniques capable of monitoring the stress/strain evolution on the scale of the detailed information presented by the numerical predictions.

Experimental techniques based on high energy synchrotron X-ray diffraction are being perfected [4] to the state where the spatial resolution approaches the scale of typical inclusions, but further development is still needed. Hence, the detailed contour results of FEM-simulations are not at present readily evaluated experimentally. However, volume average stresses and strains over many inclusions can today be characterised by neutron diffraction [5,6]. It is the aim of the present work to quantify experimentally the extent to which volume average phase strains as determined by FEM cell-modelling are in agreement with experimentally observable quantities.

MATERIAL CHARACTERISATION

The material considered is a pure aluminium based composite containing 10vol% SiC whiskers and fabricated by a powder metallurgical route described in [7]. The SiC-whiskers supplied by Mandoval Ltd., UK, have a mean diameter of 1 μ m and following extrusion the average aspect ratio was found to be approximately 7. A neutron diffraction texture analysis verified that more than 70vol% of the whiskers are aligned with their $\langle 111 \rangle$ texture component within 7 degrees to the extrusion axis. The matrix texture of the extruded composite was also characterised by neutron diffraction and showed a strong $\langle 111 \rangle$ fibre texture with more than 35vol% of the grains oriented with their $\langle 111 \rangle$ lattice direction parallel to the extrusion axis.

In the idealised cell-model considered here the local strains around the inclusion grows very large during thermo mechanical loading, and hence an appropriate constitutive behaviour of the matrix material must be characterised to equally large strain levels. This is accomplished by elevated temperature compression tests performed on $\varnothing 6$ mm cylindrical specimens of 6mm height. The materials characterisation is performed to strains of approximately 1., and at temperatures of 20, 100, 200, 300, 400 and 500°C. The experimental results described by a modified voce type equation are shown in Fig.1 displaying the materials input to the numerical simulations.

NEUTRON DIFFRACTION

Neutron diffraction is an attractive tool for probing bulk residual/internal strains in crystalline materials and has matured tremendously during the last decade [8,9]. It is based on traditional Bragg scattering experiments, whereby a selected lattice plane spacing, d_{hkl} , is used as an internal strain gauge. By the diffraction nature of the technique it provides the ability to monitor the individual phase strains in the two phases of the composite.

The initial thermal strains are characterised by comparing lattice parameters measured in the composite with those obtained from samples of the pure aluminium matrix material as well as a sample of “free” SiC whiskers contained within a sealed quartz tube. The in-situ straining of the composite samples while monitoring the evolution of phases strains, is accomplished using a loading rig developed for the neutron spectrometer [10].

Fig. 1: Thermo mechanical behaviour of the matrix material as determined by elevated temperature compression tests.

In the investigation we focus only on the lattice strains along the extrusion/loading axis. The inclusion lattice strain response is characterised by measuring on the SiC_{111} reflection of the cubic SiC whiskers, which is the orientation predominantly aligned along the extrusion axis. For the matrix lattice strain response we use the Al_{111} reflection which has also proven to be the dominating texture component for the matrix material after extrusion. The sample of the 10vol% composite is loaded in uniaxial tension to a total deformation of 10%.

FEM CELL-MODELLING

The numerical simulations are based on a 2D axisymmetric mesh with a single embedded inclusion. It may be argued that 3D simulations are more appropriate, however, the less cpu-intensive 2D-simulations do, render a guidance to how well these idealised numerical simulation procedures do render results in agreement with experimental evidence.

The FEM cell-model is shown in Fig.2 giving the relative dimensions of the model, which is constraint to maintain straight surfaces along the free outer surface ($x=0.2$) as well as along the free top surface ($y=1.0$). The constitutive behaviour of the matrix alloy has been described above and is readily included as a elastic, isotropic hardening plastic material with temperature dependent Young's moduli and hardening characteristics, whereas the inclusion is assumed to behave purely elastic with no temperature dependent properties.

The initial phase of the numerical simulation is an incremental cooling and subsequently the model is incrementally strained towards a total deformation of 10% at room temperature. Lack of convergence typically prevents us from reaching 10% total strain, as the local strain grows very large, and in-fact may exceed the extent to which the materials behaviour has been characterised.

The simulations are done using the implicit ABAQUS code using 760 8-node biquadratic elements and is run as a sequential executing job on the Silicon Graphics Power Challenge computer at Risø National Laboratory.

Fig. 2: FEM cell-model showing the idealised axisymmetric mesh and its relative dimensions.

DISCUSSION

The initial phase of the numerical simulation is a step wise free thermal contraction of the composite from a selected temperature. In the present investigation we have simulated this cooling process from temperatures ranging from 500°C to 100°C, with 500°C being the highest temperature at which the materials data are available, and which is close to the actual extrusion temperature. The results in terms of volume average elastic strains in the extrusion direction are presented in Fig.3.

In contrast to the linear behaviour expected from purely elastic materials properties [11], we note the effect of both plasticity and temperature dependency giving rise to gradient variations with temperature. The results of neutron diffraction investigations show a residual thermal strain in the matrix of 618×10^{-6} while the inclusion thermal strain was measured to be -1395×10^{-6} . These results are incorporated in Fig.3 as horizontal dotted lines showing that whereas the inclusion results point towards a “stress-free” temperature of 470°C, then the matrix residual strain level indicates a much lower temperature near 175°C. Among the two phases of the composite the purely elastic inclusions are the simplest internal strain gauge of the two; one which is not prone to any relaxation phenomena related to creep or diffusion though it is expected that the numerical simulations would render an upper bound on realistic observable thermal strains of the inclusions, as the simulations are done on an idealised perfectly aligned system. This points towards the fact that the realistic “stress-free” temperature is in fact close to the extrusion temperature near 500°C. On the other hand when looking at the matrix response experiments indicate a much lower thermal residual strain level than would arise by cooling from 500°C. It may be argued that the matrix response is merely a measure on a specific hkl-reflection of the polycrystalline aggregate and that single crystal anisotropy and choice of hkl-reflection affects the observable strain levels. However; aluminium is not a very anisotropic metal with the stiff $\langle 111 \rangle$ -orientation being only 9% stiffer than the typical macroscopic moduli. It is evident that the idealised numerical

predictions to a strong extent over estimates the matrix residual strain level as compared to the volume average matrix strain measured by neutron diffraction over a volume containing a large number of inclusions. The relative low level of matrix residual strains may point towards the lack of adequate relaxation phenomena in the materials description, however, the matrix strain level is to be balanced by the inclusion strains where we observe good correlation using a “stress-free” temperature of 500°C. This is hence indicating that the idealised FEM cell-model, at least based on volume average values of elastic strains, does not perform very well in terms of predicting the matrix deformation, while there is good correlation between experiments and simulations when it comes to the simple elastically deforming inclusions.

Fig. 3: Thermal residual strains in the two phases of the composite. Here shown as a function of the temperature from which the numerical simulation of the cooling sequence was initiated. Dotted lines indicate residual strain levels as measured by neutron diffraction.

Following the simulation of the generation of thermal mis-match strain during cooling we proceed to room temperature loading in uniaxial tension. These simulations are based on the cooling sequence from 500-20°C as predicted above, and hence originates from a situation where the initial volume average inclusion strain nicely resembles the level observed experimentally, while the volume average matrix strain is about 75% higher than observed experimentally. The numerical results shown in Fig.4 and are to be compared with the experimental results from the neutron diffraction experiments in Fig.5. The numerical results are qualitatively in agreement with the experimental observations, however, some discrepancies are observed on the numerical levels.

It is evident that the evolution of elastic phase strains in the inclusion is much stronger from the cell model predictions than can be observed experimentally, even in this situation where the initial residual strain level is accurately estimated. An obvious reason for part of the discrepancies is that the inclusions of the real composite are not as perfectly aligned as assumed by the model. For the matrix response we also observe that the numerical simulations over estimates the evolution of elastic phase strains. It is, however, noticed that the discrepancies throughout the total strain range appears to be attributed entirely to the lack of correspondence in the initial thermally induced residual strain level at the outset of the loading sequence.

The overall correspondence between numerical predictions and experimental characterisation of the phase strain evolution would have been improved had we selected a lower “stress-free” temperature, however, at present it would be pure speculation as to specifying a more proper “stress-free” temperature than the 500°C at which the matrix material does still retain some measurable strength.

Fig. 4: Numerical predictions of the volume average elastic strain $\langle \epsilon_Y \rangle$ in matrix (O) and in the inclusion (●) along the loading direction.

Fig. 5: Experimental characterisation of the volume average elastic strain $\langle \varepsilon_y \rangle$ in matrix (O) and in the inclusions (●) along the loading direction.

CONCLUSION

The present investigation has highlighted the applicability of the neutron diffraction technique in the evaluation of an FEM cell-model approach of the thermo mechanical behaviour of composites. The investigation has highlighted how the utilisation of this novel experimental technique provides a step towards an evaluation of the micro mechanical value of FEM cell-models at a level of detail not achievable with other techniques at present. Such models have until recently mostly been evaluated by their capability to predict macroscopic deformation characteristics. The diffraction experiments has shown that the numerical predictions of phase strains are in qualitative agreement with observations, though there are some discrepancies in the quantitative estimates. We have pointed out that one of the reasons for the discrepancies is the idealised alignment of the inclusion in the model, however, the experimental results also point towards problems in realistic predictions of the relative strain levels between matrix and inclusions as it is not possible to define a single “stress-free” temperature in the simulations which render realistic thermal residual strains in both phases of the composite. It may be added that possibly problems do also remain in verifying a proper description of the thermo mechanical behaviour of the matrix material when being part of a composite as compared to the behaviour when being a “free” monolithic material.

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